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Determinants Of Job Stress Among Academic Staff Of Public Universities In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Stress is inevitable in every works of life, though it may differ in its intensity depending on the nature of work. This study investigated the determinants of job stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State. The study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. The study population comprised of 3,983 academic staff in the three government owned Universities in Rivers State. The sample size was 768 and a multistage sampling procedure was employed. The instrument for data collection in this study was an adopted questionnaire titled, Questionnaire on Stress and its Determinant Factors (QSiDF)". Data analysis was carried out using percentage and Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed that, statistically significant relationship was found between stress and factors such as workload (N = 747, $r = 0.85$, $p = 0.01$); job requirement (N = 747, $r = 0.70$, $p = 0.04$); and condition of working environment (N = 747, $r = 0.53$, $p = 0.03$). However, the result showed a non-significant relationship between stress and remuneration (N = 747, $r = -0.14$, $p = 0.22$); and availability of resources (N = 747, $r = -0.33$, $p = 0.15$). The study concluded that the determinants of job stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State were workload, job requirement, and condition of working environment. It was recommended that, the government should employ more teaching staffs in the Universities to ease the workload on the workers. Also, the government should consider increasing the remuneration of the lecturers in this trying economic times, in order to ease their stress.

Keywords: Academic Staff, Determinants, Job stress, Public Universities

INTRODUCTION

Stress represents a situation where a person is under pressure and does not have sufficient ability to cope with it. According to Abebe et al. (2018) stress is how the body responds to a demand or threatening experiences. You feel stressed when you are under pressure to do something or when you have to deal with adverse situations. Etiologically stress is derived from the Latin word "stringere"; which means the experience of physical hardship, starvation, torture and pains. Stress and its manifestations, such as anxiety depression, fatigue and burnout, have always been seen as a common problem among people in different profession and occupation (Shin et al., 2017). The American Psychological Association (2018) defined stress as one of interaction between the situation and the individual. It is the psychological and physical state that results when the resources of the individual are not sufficient to cope with the demands and pressures of the situation (APA, 2018). Thus, stress is more likely in some situations than others and in some staffs than others.

Job stress may be less for staff if the working environment is conducive. Healthy work environment is vital to the retention and recruitment of academic professionals and the sustainability of the education systems (Pino & Rossini, 2014). Workplace environment described the surrounding conditions for the

employee in performing their duties. The work environment can be composed of physical conditions and it can also be related to factors such as work processes or procedures. This environment can affect ones' health either positively or negatively. The factors of working environment includes the facilities in doing the job, comfortable workplace, safety workplace and the degree of noise. The workplace environment plays an important role in job satisfaction and well-being of the workers (Parvin, 2014). Ironically, there is a need to provide a healthy work environment that can protect the employee mental and physical well-being especially for secondary school lecturers.

Unavailability of facilities and equipment needed to get a job done could exert more stress on the workers as the he will be managing or improvising to get the job done. Nnabuiife et al. (2014) posited that there is growing evidence that schools no longer provide the low stress working environment that they once did. As a result of the changing landscape of education, job stress levels are generally high. To reduce stress, adequate facilities and equipment need to be set up which will make them to see the need to look for opportunities to relax and get the job done, distinguish tasks that absolutely must be done from those that are simply nice to do, determine what must be done now, what can wait, and what requires consistent small bursts of activity.

Job requirement is another factor which is associated with stress among academic staff of public universities (Kinnunen, 2016). Working in a job with high demands and low control or being engaged in effortful work that provides low rewards in terms of money, esteem, promotion prospects and job security increases the risk of depression by about 80% within a few years (Siegel 2018). Robust and consistent evidence exists from Stansfeld (2017) that, high demands and low decision latitude and high effort and low rewards are prospective risk factors for common mental disorders and that the psychosocial work environment is important for mental health and prevalence of stress. The stress level may even increase when there is a high level of job requirement with poor remuneration.

Remuneration refers to the payment one receives for the job done. As stated by Stevens (2014), remuneration is the entire compensation package that an employee gets in exchange for the services he/she renders to the employer. Characteristically, this could entail monetary rewards, also known as wage or salary, as well as non-monetary rewards. Other researchers also noted employee remuneration as a product of several factors in an organization, including work-related action, specifically the employee's performance (Gomez-Mejia et. al., 2019). According to Oyebamiji (2014), remuneration is essential for continuous operation and progressiveness because it stimulates employee's willingness to be committed to an organization. Oyebamiji (2014) found that good remuneration predicts job satisfaction collectively and independently predict job performance and stress levels, particularly with a high workload.

Workload in form of regularly assess time requirements and design reasonable deadlines; ensure that working hours are predictable and more reasonable (International Labour Organization, 2016). A large number of studies show that lecturers in higher institution are exposed to a workload that results particularly in stress. According to Rusli et al. (2014), high job demand, increased environmental exposures and overtime work has increased the stress level. Likewise, Ngari et al. (2014) established that, school lecturers and administrators experienced stress in their work. More than half of the respondents recorded high levels of stress resulting from their school workload and other responsibilities. Klassen et al. (2014), found out that lecturers had greater workload stress, greater classroom stress from student behaviors, and lower classroom management self-efficacy. Lecturers with greater workload stress had greater classroom management self-efficacy, whereas lecturers with greater classroom stress had lower self-efficacy and lower job satisfaction. The study of Putter (2003) on stress factors among lecturers in schools of industry showed that, lecturers experience high levels of stress with regard to time management, work-related stressors, professional distress, discipline and motivation and professional investment. These, could affect the health of the academic staff with negative consequences on their health and their job performance.

In Rivers State, public universities are three with two State-owned and one Federal-owned. Though the two State-owned were not affected by industrial strike, the later was affected, which left some of the academic staff without salaries for eight months leading to starvation, and survival difficulties. This

scenario could be so stressful to the academic staff. Yet, several agitations have focused on the students returning to school, leaving the welfare of the staff without adequate attention, even among scholars. This is because, the bulk of recent studies on stress are focused on different work settings, even the ones carried out in the universities had focused on students, leaving stress and its determinants among lecturers inadequately revealed. Hence, this study focused on the prevalence of stress and its determinants among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study following research questions were raised for the study:

1. What is the relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
3. What is the relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
4. What is the relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?
5. What is the relationship between condition of working environmental and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were stated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.
4. There is no significant relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.
5. There is no significant relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive correlational research design. The study population comprised of 3,983 academic staff in the three government owned Universities in Rivers State. The sample size was 768 and a multistage sampling procedure was employed. In the first stage, a simple random sampling technique was used to select five faculties in each of the Universities; at the second stage, the simple random sampling technique was also used to select ten departments (from each selected faculty) in each of the selected Universities; at the third stage, the simple random sampling was used to select the determined number of respondents from each institution. The instrument for data collection in this study was an adopted questionnaire titled, Questionnaire on Stress and its Determinant Factors (QSiDF)". The instrument consisted of three sections. Section A addressed the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents. It consisted of five items on a multiple response format which include; age, gender, marital status, family size and years of work experience. Section B focused was designed to elicit responses on academic stressors on a modified scale rated under four categories of responses ranging from: causing no stress (0), mild stress (1), moderate stress (2), and causing severe stress (3) to indicate intensity of stress caused by each item. Section C focused on the determinants of stress which was self-structured by the researcher. Data analysis was carried out using percentage and Pearson Correlation at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The results of the study are shown below:

Table 1: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Workload	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.85	Very High relationship
	N	747	747	
Workload	Pearson correlation	0.85	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 1 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.85$, indicating a very high relationship. Thus, the relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was very high.

Table 2: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Remuneration	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	-0.14	Very low negative relationship
	N	747	747	
Remuneration	Pearson correlation	-0.14	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 2 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.14$, indicating a very low relationship. Thus, the relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was very low.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Job requirement	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.71	High relationship
	N	747	747	
Job requirement	Pearson correlation	0.71	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 3 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.71$, indicating a high relationship. Thus, the relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was high.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Availability	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	-0.33	Low negative relationship
	N	747	747	
Availability	Pearson correlation	-0.33	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 4 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.33$, indicating a low negative relationship. Thus, the relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was low.

Table 5: Pearson Correlation showing relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Condition of working environment	Remark
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.53	Moderate relationship
	N	747	747	
Working environment	Pearson correlation	0.53	1	
	N	747	747	

Guide: 0.00-0.19 = very low, 0.20-0.39 = low, 0.40-0.59 = moderate, 0.60-0.79 = high and 0.80 above is very high relationship

Table 5 showed the Pearson Correlation of relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed a correlation coefficient, $r = 0.53$, indicating a moderate relationship. Thus, the relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was moderate.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 6: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Workload	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.85	H_0 rejected
	Sig.		0.01*	
	N	747	747	
Workload	Pearson correlation	0.85	1	
	Sig.	0.01*		
	N	747	747	

***Significant; $p < 0.05$**

Table 6 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between workload and stress among academic staff as $p < 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.85$, $p = 0.01$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was rejected.

Table 7: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Remuneration	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	-0.14	H ₀ not rejected
	Sig.		0.22*	
	N	747	747	
Remuneration	Pearson correlation	-0.14	1	
	Sig	0.22*		
	N	747	747	

***Not Significant; p>0.05**

Table 7 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff as $p > 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = -0.14$, $p = 0.22$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was not rejected.

Table 8: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Job requirement	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.70	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.04*	
	N	747	747	
Job requirement	Pearson correlation	0.70	1	
	Sig	0.04*		
	N	747	747	

***Significant; p<0.05**

Table 8 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff as $p < 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.70$, $p = 0.04$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between job requirement and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was rejected.

Table 9: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Availability	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	-0.33	H ₀ not rejected
	Sig.		0.15*	
	N	747	747	
Availability	Pearson correlation	-0.33	1	
	Sig	0.15*		
	N	747	747	

***Not Significant; p>0.05**

Table 9 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff as $p > 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = -0.33$, $p = 0.15$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between availability of resources and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was not rejected.

Table 10: Pearson Correlations analysis showing relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State

Variables		Stress	Condition of working environment	Decision
Stress	Pearson correlation	1	0.53	H ₀ rejected
	Sig.		0.03*	
	N	747	747	
Working environment	Pearson correlation	0.53	1	
	Sig	0.03*		
	N	747	747	

***Significant; p<0.05**

Table 10 presents the Pearson Correlations analysis on relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities. The result revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff as $p < 0.05$ ($N = 747$, $r = 0.53$, $p = 0.03$). Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between condition of working environment and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are discussed below:

The result showed that the relationship between workload and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was very high and statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = 0.85$, $p = 0.01$). The finding of the study was anticipated because of the personal observation made during the data collection, where some were always busy with their work and may scarcely have time for other things. The finding of this study is akin to that of Onowhapor (2018) whose study in Ghana found that the sources of stress are high for workers with high workload. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Siegal et al. (2016) who found that some of the major sources of occupational stress affects workers may be more severe for those with pressing workload. The finding of this study is in keeping with that of Oyewole and Popoola (2021) study on occupational stress and burnout among lecturers in Nigerian Universities which showed a relationship between workload and stress level. The finding of this study is also in consonance with that of Adeyemi and Adeyinka, (2017) whose study on occupational stress and job satisfaction among Nigerian university lecturers which showed a relationship between workload and stress among academic staff. The finding of this study is also in consonance with that of Owoeye and Iyiola, (2019) carried out a study on Occupational Stress and Burnout among Nigerian University Lecturers which showed a relationship between workload and stress among academic staff. This similarity found between the previous studies and the present one could be attributed to the homogeneity of the study population.

The finding of the study revealed that the relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State was very low. This finding is not surprising as remuneration is a vital aspect of life which makes life and survival more stressful cum the current economic stress on individuals. The finding of the study corroborates that of Adeyemi-Bello, and Ogunyemi, (2018) on occupational stress among academic staff in Nigerian Universities which showed a relationship between remuneration and stress among academic staff of Universities. The finding of this study gives credence to that of Segal et al. (2016) who found that some of the major sources of occupational stress include: lack of job security and fear of being laid off; heavy work load and overtime due to staff cutbacks; pressure to perform to meet rising expectations with adequate reward or job satisfaction; role conflicts and unclear expectations; poor or uncomfortable working conditions; lack of control over one's job; inadequate wages/salary or benefits; lack of participation in decision company policies making; poor communication; poor relationships among main agent, coworker. The finding of this study is similar to that of Collingan et al. (2013) who outlined the various sources of occupational stress to include; remuneration and work

environment which includes inadequate arrangement of hospital equipment and materials, increase temperature, lighting problem, and lack of space among others, negative workload.

The finding of the study indicated that the relationship between job requirement and stress was high and was statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = 0.70$, $p = 0.04$). The finding of this study corroborates that of Nwokeoma et al. (2019) whose study on work-related stress management among Nigeria public workers which showed that respondents adopted stress coping strategies irrespective of the job posting. The similarity between the present study and that of Nwokeoma and colleagues could be due to the homogeneity of the study population. The finding of the study showed that the relationship between availability of resources and stress was low and was not statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = -0.33$, $p = 0.15$). The result showed that the relationship between condition of working environment and stress was moderate and statistically significant ($N = 747$, $r = 0.53$, $p = 0.03$). The finding of this study corroborates that of Nwokeoma et al. (2019) whose study on work-related stress management among Nigeria public workers which showed that respondents adopted stress coping strategies irrespective of the job posting. The similarity between the present study and that of Nwokeoma and colleagues could be due to the homogeneity of the study population.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the study concluded that the determinants of job stress among academic staff of public universities in Rivers State were workload, job requirement, and condition of working environment.

1. The result showed workload a major determinant, hence, the government should employ more teaching staffs in the Universities to ease the workload on the workers.
2. The result also showed remuneration affected stress thus, the government should consider increasing the remuneration of the lecturers in this trying economic times, in order to ease their stress.
3. The management of the higher institutions of learning map out recreational activities to improve workers' access to stress management strategies, and cultivate a healthy working condition that improves staff's health.
4. The management of the Universities in Rivers State should help the lecturers ease their stress by providing all needed resources to make their job easy and less stressful.
5. Government should make the lecturers comfortable in their work environment by building more infrastructure for them, this will make them to be more relaxed, focused and discharge their duties better with minimal stress.

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